

PERCEPTIVE FEATURES OF THE UZBEK IDIOMATIC WORDS AND THEIR ANALOGOUS IN ENGLISH

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Annotation. *The advancing of the Uzbek semantics and learning ways to deal with language, particularly, issues of mental semantics have been investigated in the article. The outcomes show that mental methodology and techniques for mental language materials did regulation of lexical units of the Uzbek language, as the materials of the Uzbek language show the reasons of calculated association of phonetic units, including the semantic component of mental etymological association were enlightened in the article. The primary qualities of informal units depended on reasonable association. A few informal expressions of the Uzbek language were converted into English with their counterparts. An assortment of Uzbek language materials depends on the view of the real world, information, potential open doors semantic memory of individuals. The article is committed to the exploration of ways of idiomaticity in the Uzbek word development. It portrays different reasons for the development of idiomaticity in compound words. The point of the exploration work is the investigation of the mental part of colloquial expressions of the Uzbek language. The job of mental systems in word arrangement and verbalization of language units is considered as one of the effective issues of semantics. The writer of the article breaks down the mental bases of the development of informal words in the Uzbek language. Reasonable metonymy, applied similitude, and metaphonymy were exhibited as fundamental mental systems in the arrangement of colloquial words. Besides, the article covers the issues of causing colloquial words because of's how individuals might interpret the world, their appearance in person's comprehension, and the course of an impression of mental instruments in the arrangement of the idea.*

Keywords: *idiomaticity, conceptual metaphor, conceptual metonymy, metaphonymy, equivalence, motivation, idiomatic words.*

Introduction. *The finish of the XX century is recognized by its emphasis on anthropocentrism, a new logical worldview that concentrates on the issues connected with the element of a human being in semantics.*

Concentrating on the language units according to extra-semantic variables like correspondence, the otherworldliness of language clients, their insight into the world, cooperative reasoning, public and social perspective have turned into the fundamental concern. Since the investigation of the mental premise of the arrangement of Uzbek informal words in near perspective remaining parts a significant issue on account of their capability to conceptualize the universe of the language clients. As is referred to, colloquial words fill in to protect and communicate individuals' information because they comprehended the world. Particularly, compound words arise at the moment that discernment and correspondence agree. There might be a few language units in the construction of informal compound words based on the economy of language standards. Compound words must mirror an individual's physical, social, and chronicled insight. The mental premise of compound words, which is impossible to miss in different languages, empowers to concentrate on the issues of relations among language and culture, language and ethnos and to characterize the meaning of language units; the way that prompts study colloquial compound words from a mental perspective in etymology.

The expression "idiomaticity" turned into a focal thought in various explores in the second from last quarter of the XIX century, and the current term was utilized by Ch. Bally towards phraseological units in phonetics. As indicated by him, idiomaticity is a phraseological unit that is a consequence of losing its denotative significance from the semantic mark of view being indivisible from one another (Bally, Ch., 1961). A.A. Reformatzkiy gave the accompanying definition to the expression "idiomaticity": "they can't be converted into another language in the same words. Such phonetic unit is called expression and their overall state is referred to idiomaticity as" [Reformatzkiy, A.A., 2006]. As per the researchers, the expression "idiomaticity" signifies a bunch of colloquialisms. "Oxford Dictionary of Idioms" incorporates straightforward words, inferred words, compound words, and phraseological units. We expect that idiomaticity ought to be contemplated towards every language not overall be that as it may, independently. Charles F Hockett and Glaser R. in their work recognized that phraseological units, as well as single words and indeed, even morphemes, can be informal. Informal units exhibit the quirks of the language potential introducing data of the language speakers' creative mind of the world and how they are seen. As to A.I. Smirnitkiy general importance of idiomaticity of a compound word isn't subject to the mix of parts. As well as Ch. Carr and O. Jespersen notes that

the significance of an informal compound word as a language unit can't be perceived by its blend of parts. ^[1]

As indicated by I. Arnold, a compound word becomes colloquial when it loses the level of its inspiration, since one of its components isn't utilized in its genuine significance. As is known, the job of inspiration is significant in word development, when there is no need for extra information to comprehend the significance of an inferred word. Notwithstanding, if the instance of idiomaticity replaces inspiration there is a need for extra information from the recipient which is found in the compound words. Informal compound words are associated with a semantic characteristic of a word. It is difficult to characterize its importance based on the example of compound word construction and it should be expressed that the significance of colloquial compound words has an extraordinary significance. Colloquial compound words are not decided from a static condition of a language yet characterized through a unique state and their importance is considered as an aftereffect of figurative or metonymical change. In this sense, we decipher idiomaticity and inspiration as a peculiarity exceptional to intensify words. Idiomaticity is unconventional to a larger part of the Uzbek compound words. The semantic volume of compound words is bigger than designed compound words. Their arrangement is viewed as a more muddled process than designed compound words, henceforth they are connected with as re-cognizance of the world. The peculiarity of idiomaticity might be seen in the progress of A.Hajiev, B.Madaliev, and M.Mirtajiev, but they don't refer to "idiomaticity". A.Hajiev states that words may have figurative significance and states that: "The importance of compound words will not show up because of the blend of parts, for example, itog'iz, (it - canine, og'iz-mouth) in English snapdragon, otquloq (ot - horse, quloq - ear) it's English correspondences are roan; dock". One can see that the overall importance of examined words is associated not one or the other with the first nor with the subsequent part. The informal nature of these words comes out of the appearance of a plant name yet not the body of the creature. How do idiomaticity processes happen in compound words? A person goes through various mental cycles in the development of colloquial compound words. The accompanying mental instruments effectively partake in the development of informal compound words:

1. Calculated analogy.
2. Calculated metonymy.
3. Metaphonymy.

¹ Arnold I.V. (1986). The English Word. Moskva: Visshaya shkola.

By the last quarter of the XX century "hypothesis of illustration" was presented in the book "Analogies We Live by" distributed by J. Lakoff and M. Johnson. The substance of the current hypothesis lies in the origination presented by G. Lakoff and M. Johnson, for example, the new nature of an allegory not as an expressive method but rather as a reasonable semantic peculiarity. As per them, analogies exist in people's applied framework for articulation through language. All in all, an allegory is particular to thinking, and semantic allegories are external articulations of the current peculiarity, "analogies are not just in our regular daily existence, in our language as well as they are in our reasoning and exercises. Our consistently, applied framework, our thoughts and activities to their embodiment are metaphoric". Thus, the analogy isn't just a method for articulation, yet additionally a peculiarity, which is connected with thinking and culture. Hence, calculated analogies are not such basic inferred implications showed up just based on a basic change of meaning however the consequence of a complex mental cycle which happens in human creatures comprehension. Our perceptions, in this regard, show that a theoretical similitude is the most useful method of another name. A theoretical allegory is viewed as a significant component in the development of colloquial compound words. J. Lakoff and M. Johnson showed two areas in the development of an allegorical inferred importance in mental semantics, for example, source area and target space. As indicated by them, there is bury impact of a casing and situation behind similitudes. "Source area" is an individual's arrangement of information essentially on the premise of involvement, though the "target space" is similarly less explained what's more characterized as unavoidable information.^[2]

While an important change happens through an allegory, an individual utilizes the units existing in the design of the jargon of a language that serves to be a "source space". Concerning the "target area" an individual uses a new inferred significance shaped of instant language units in his/her reasoning. As per Ayvor A. Richards, "thinking itself is allegorical, it happens based on examination and simply on this mark of the language analogy shows up". Jose Ortega-I-Rasset likewise progresses that "illustration isn't just a method of articulation, however, it is a fundamental instrument of reasoning". Metonymy has been contemplated as an elaborate means to communicate symbolism. As V.N.Teliya states, there

² Ayvor A. Richards. (1990). Metafora [Metaphor]. Teoriya metafora [Theory of Metaphor]: Sbornik: Per. s.ang.,fr., isp., pols., yaz. / Vstup. St. i sost. N.D.Artyunovoy; Obsh. red. N.D.Artyunovoy i M.A.Jurniskiy. Moskva: Progress.

is a typical connection between importance through metonymy which shows up based on an important move without a hitch. The acquaintance of another methodology with metonymy by Z. Kovecses and G. Radden has changed and it is quite significant: "metonymy is a mental interaction, where one idea is a vehicle and one more idea is an objective which is given by mental accomplishing the objective space inside one area or glorified mental models". It should be focused on that there is thought ordinariness in this definition. It is clarified by the way that ideas are the pieces of admired mental models, subsequently, they will be in like manner connection. The hypothesis proposed on similitude and metonymy by G. Lakoff and M. Johnson is of extraordinary importance. As indicated by them, metonymic ideas are fed on the premise of information aggregated by people, they will be more clear than allegorical ideas, typically metonymy ideas have accurate physiological or acquainted qualifications. We support the thought progressed by the researchers on mental etymology Ungerer, F., Schmid, H.- J. who separated the most dynamic metonymic models of word development: (Types of Stand for Relations in Metonymies) PART FOR WHOLE (everyone ready and available) Entire FOR PART (to top off the vehicle). The arrangement of informal compound words encourages the transaction of the significance of a calculated sort. V. Croft and D. Cruse express that a calculated metonymy incorporates two spaces: a vehicle area and an objective space. As per them, the assignment of a vehicle area is to characterize the construction of an objective space in metonymy. The information is examined, applying an exceptionally logical strategy, and utilizing in a similar and differentiating style in a method for inspiring the idiomaticity in the semantic contrasts between the Uzbek and English languages.

Compound words are dissected as per the inspiration and idiomaticity. During the time spent moving of the significance of an applied metonymy type the name of the part communicates the entirety. For example, in Uzbek and English substantial lexemes express the highlights curious to an individual and occasions and peculiarities connected with it in the construction of the colloquial compound words *kalla*, - head: *xomkalla* - a dull individual (*xom* - crude, uncooked, *kalla* - head). What could be compared to this lexeme in English is an imbecile. One thing is clear that colloquial compound words can be shaped not just through a reasonable similitude or a calculated metonymy yet in addition as an outcome of the joining of both reasonable peculiarities. Thus, it would be sensible to discuss one more new term in etymology - metaphonymy. The term metaphonymy was first presented in etymology by L. Goossens. The researcher was quick to focus on the combined interaction of metonymy and analogy and called it a peculiarity of metaphonymy. As per him, there

is a complex instrument that joins both metonymy and illustration in the language.^[3] As of now, metaphonymy has become one of the fundamental models of conceptualization of the truth. L. Goossens separates two essential kinds of metaphonymy:

1) metonymy inside an analogy; 2) representation from metonymy.

The substance of the gathering one is portrayed by the moving of the importance inside "vehicle space". Metonymy is figuratively re-considered and transforms into a component of the entire space. L. Goossens breaks down this hypothesis through the following show phrases: stay quiet off - "be upset for what one has simply said". The overall significance of a given metonymy is a metonymy inside a representation. The examination of these models shows that allegorical, metonymic, and metaphonymic inferred implications are the aftereffect of a complex mental cycle. Certain information acquired because of understanding the world by a person lies behind these inferred implications. The development of metonymic and allegorical importance is done where human discernment and correspondence join together. The Uzbek language is wealthy in informal compound words with applied figurative importance. The accompanying three colloquial compound words can uncover the reasonable figurative significance of informal compound words in Uzbek: The Uzbek word qizilishton implies a bird with short legs, a solid, and a long nose living in the forest. (qizil - red, ishton - pants). The main part of the word qizil signifies "the shade of a blood or rubies". The arrangement of the informal compound word as a standards emeruby-hued starts things out. The part of the word qizil has a place with the mental area COLOR. This idea satisfies the errand of a "source area" in the development of a compound word and it is projected with the second part of the word. The part ishton (pants) as indicated by the referenced word reference, signifies "undies or pants, lozim - "undies of ladies in Central Asia". For "ishton" the seme long clothing is a fundamental one, it is remembered for the design of the mental space CLOTHES. There seems to mix between the first and second parts COLOR and CLOTHES of the word. At the following stage the likeness among COLOR and CLOTHES which is a "source area" and BIRD "target space" is characterized. The similarity is that the bird's quills are red, the piece of the human body where s/he has clothing. The client of the Uzbek language depends on the ordered and subcategorized theoretical frameworks and based on the information in cognizance of the world, for

³ Bally Ch. (1961). Fransuskaya stilistika [French stylistics]. Moskva: Izdatelstvo Innostranniye Literaturi.

example, because of the way that the bird's back part has a red quill supposed as "qizilishton". In English, the very bird is called a woodpecker; the way that the bird eats worms in the tree and its activity connected with cleaning trees are considered as far as naming. The Uzbek naming, most likely, focused on its appearance concerning English they focused on its action. It is reasoned that each culture has its specific manner of development the etymological perspective on the world.

In Uzbek, there is a word which implies an illness "otpaypoq" "shin-hand joints stable solidified paws palms side (base) twisted around and paw". (ot - horse, paypoq - socks). The "ot" part of the current compound word signifies "a strong hooped plant-eating tamed warm-blooded creature with a streaming mane and tail, utilized for riding, hustling, and to convey and pull burdens" and it happens in the calculated area ANIMAL. The idea ANIMAL is considered to have a wide area and it satisfies the capacity of "source area". The part of the compound word "paypoq" signifies "thigh, calf, or adjusting, generally made of manufactured shoes". In this compound word, the part child why this word has a spot from the Artifact calculated space is that the socks were made by people. In the construction of the compound word the seme of the primary part becomes dynamic. In the arrangement of the colloquial compound words, the language client thinks about is the way that pony feet don't twist and socks are not profound

whenever they are worn. Based on these signs an illness which is seen as inhuman creatures' is called out paypoq - horse socks. The units which were subcategorized from two theoretical areas coordinated disregarded the third new idea DISEASE. It is viewed as "an objective space". In contrast with English, informal compound words framed with applied metonymic significance are broadly utilized in Uzbek. The compound word "ayiqtovon" signifies "a sort of under a year lush plant". (ayiq - bear, tovon - heel). The part "ayiq" of this informal compound word signifies "towels, wooly, fat, enormous, warm-blooded creatures, wild creature". This word has affiliated importance as well as counting club-footed, for example, pence were off-base, slanted. "Ayiq" has a place with the idea of ANIMAL of the mental space. The affiliated importance of "ayiq" and "oyoq" paw becomes dynamic in the arrangement of "ayiqtovon". The second part of the compound word - remuneration signifies "part of the rear of the leg". This lexeme semantically is remembered for the construction of the space of the idea BODY. In the arrangement of the compound word, the same soul becomes dynamic. [4]

⁴ Croft W., D.Alan Cruse. (2004). Cognitive Linguistics. New York by Cambridge University Press.

During the time spent the arrangement of the colloquial compound word "ayiqtovon" ideas ANIMAL and BODY satisfy the capacity of a "vehicle space", where the metonymic significance move, which reflects WHOLE for PART connection, comes to presence. Because of a reasonable joining of the significance of ideas ANIMAL, what's more BODY an idea PLANT, which is the "target area", shows up. In English, this plant's tone looks like the shade of the margarine and its blossom looks like a cup and on the premise of this looks like "buttercup" is shaped. In Uzbek a troubled individual is designated "shorpeshona" and that implies a "despondent what's the more unfortunate man or lady". (shor - salt(y), peshona - temple). The principal part of the compound word "shor" signifies "over the top salts, enduring, trouble; wretchedness". The lexeme "shor" is semantically remembered for the mental space TASTE. This lexeme is additionally utilized in metaphorical signifying "enduring, trouble; hopelessness"; the implications become dynamic in the arrangement of the compound word "shorpeshona". The second part of the compound word "peshana" signifies "deformities of eyebrow hair, brow". The lexeme "peshana" is remembered for a few phraseological units. "He could release a limit of the brow, to see the temple" signifies "as the destinies order, as destiny (has) willed". The subsequent part "peshana" of the colloquial compound word "shorpeshona" is in the mental space of the idea BODY. In the development of the present compound word the ideas TASTE and BODY satisfy the capacity of the "vehicle space". Metonymic exchange of significance is done through a piece of the body which implies peshona. That is, in the example of PART for WHOLE. The cycle which occurred in the development of the informal compound word "shorpeshana" signifies "horrible destiny composed on his brow". The idea of HUMAN BEING is "an objective area". This colloquial compound word ("shorpeshana") in English will be "unfortunate". Utilizing metaphonymic meaning the accompanying words are examined taking into account the guideline of "part for the entire": analogy from metonymy.

The colloquial compound word "qiziloyoq" signifies "a long-legged bird who lives along the water and fish". In the development of the current compound word its first part a lexeme - "qizil" has a figurative exchange (here bird's red leg is taken into thought). The lexeme "qizil" (red) is in the mental space of the idea of Shading. The second part of the compound word lexeme "oyoq" (leg and foot) is semantically in the mental space of the idea BODY. During the time spent the development of the compound word a name was shaped based on PART for WHOLE, for example by the leg of the bird the entire bird was named. Because of the incorporation of the two ideas, an informal compound word "qiziloyoq" communicating a bird's name was shaped based on metaphonymy. This bird in English is

called sandpiper. As should be visible from the rundown of colloquial compound words, every one of them has an English counterpart. Yet, the statement of these implications is unique. ^[5]

Conclusion. The issue of the mental part of informal compound words is somewhat another field of examination. Informal compound words are framed of known parts to language clients and parts that are not acquired from other languages. Colloquial compound words are language units framed through mental cycles bit by bit in light of the information safeguarded in a person's acumen, showing the public social elements of the applicable society. Theoretical analogy, calculated metonymy, and metaphonymy assume an entirely significant part in the development of informal compound words. Verbalization of the perspective through analogy, metonymy also metaphonymy in languages are completed by an applied examination and characterized with the assistance of mental models. A person's information and re-appreciation of the world is distinctively seen in mental idiomatic. Satisfying J. Lakoff's thought that "our reasoning is figurative in any case" we would state "it is only our reasoning that is informal".

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